

Importance of ratification of international laws and decisions on the fight against corruption in Uzbekistan, economic-political and social-legal mechanisms.

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Abstract: The main obstacle to the success of the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan and to our progress is the disease of corruption. Speaking in this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev said, "Today, the results of our reforms are largely due to four important factors - ensuring the rule of law, fighting corruption, increasing institutional capacity and strong democratic who acknowledged that it depends on the formation of institutions. Summarizing these four factors, it can be said that the effectiveness of reforms depends on one factor, that is, the establishment of a fair social order.

Key words: Corruption, reforms, rule of law, fair social order, institutional capacity, spiritual growth.

INTRODUCTION

As mentioned above, the main obstacle to the establishment of such an order is corruption. Therefore, in his address to the Oliy Majlis, the Honorable President Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated that "the last evil that worries and disturbs me very much is the scourge of corruption." Therefore, the fight against corruption is considered the most urgent problem for Uzbekistan today, and the solution to this problem is related to spiritual growth. Enlightenment Islam plays a decisive role in the spiritual development of society, because spirituality first of all means purification of the human soul.

MAIN PART

If we consider the problems existing in the human society as a social disease, then it is more important to prevent it than to treat any disease. But for this, it is necessary to find the cause of this disease, so in order to eliminate corruption, first of all, it is necessary to find its cause. So, where is the cause of corruption?

Before talking about the cause of corruption, it is necessary to understand the meaning of this word. There are many definitions of corruption in the dictionaries, and among them, the most recognized definition is "Corruption is a criminal act associated with the abuse of official powers by an official for the purpose of increasing personal wealth." action" is the given definition. In other words,

corruption means unbridled bribery, that is, sooner or later corruption will occur if the person who received the bribe is not punished according to his crime. Therefore, the bureaucracy and the administrative command system create the ground for corruption as a result of bribery and its lack of control. The cause of corruption is the unbridled need for material wealth of an official (due to moral poverty) and the inevitability of punishment (due to weak control).

So, the concept of corruption is related to the concept of bribery, that is, corruption means bribery, and bribery means corruption. Because the meaning of the word corruption means "buying" by giving money, i.e. causing action according to one's (the money giver's) purpose. For example, paying money to enter school, paying money to study, paying money to get a job, paying money to buy votes in the election process, paying money to escape punishment for a crime, giving money to encourage people, etc. are examples of corruption. It seems that all of them are related to bribery. But even so, it is necessary to distinguish between bribery and corruption. Bribery should be understood as giving and receiving bribes between two people in order to achieve a certain goal.

Corruption refers to a situation where bribery is not between two people, but between several people, and the bribe is given to an official. Corruption is related to officials and has a systemic nature, and the initiative is on the part of the bribe giver. For example, if a teacher takes a bribe from a student to the dean, and the dean gives it to the rector, and the rector goes up, it means that the higher education system is corrupt. Or the use of bribes in the selection and placement of personnel means that this system is corrupt. The most dangerous for society is the corrupt system of personnel selection and placement. Because a person who has a position by giving money will try to get back the money he gave tomorrow. It is also dangerous because the cadres who are able to implement the reforms will be left behind, and the unqualified, low-educated and morale cadres will have to unqualifiedly deal with the implementation of the reforms. In addition, the corruption of this system leads to a decrease in the desire of young people for knowledge and spirituality.

Because where there is corruption, a person with strong knowledge and spirituality is left behind, and a person with a lot of money is appointed to a leadership position. Young people who are aware of this will stop striving for knowledge and spirituality. In order to avoid such a situation, the high level of knowledge and spirituality should be accepted as the main criteria in the personnel selection system. Where money is involved, compliance with these criteria cannot be ensured. Corruption, wherever it occurs, is a threat to society and national security. Especially if the judicial system, which is responsible for establishing order in the society, is corrupt, it is extremely dangerous for the society. In

addition, corruption in the incentive system is extremely dangerous for society. Because the injustice in the incentive system is double injustice.

Why, the fact that a deserving person is not rewarded is an injustice and, on top of that, the awarding of an unworthy person is another injustice. Usually, an unmotivated person will try to bribe and, on the contrary, a worthy person will refrain from bribery. Therefore, the fight against corruption should be strengthened, first of all, in these three systems, that is, the judicial system, the system of personnel selection and placement, and the incentive system. Curbing corruption in these systems makes it possible to overcome corruption in all spheres of social life. In the fight against corruption, the main focus should be on understanding how important the problem is, determining its cause and conditions, and finding ways to eliminate it. Based on the importance of prevention rather than treatment, it is more correct to focus on prevention rather than punishment.

In the fight against corruption, it is important to carry out preventive measures aimed at preventing crime, along with a strict struggle to ensure the inevitability of punishment. Speaking in this regard, the Honorable President Shavkat Mirziyoev said, "But can positive results be achieved only with a whip and a sword? I believe that this is not only a wrong idea, but also a profound innovation. Who will effectively carry out prevention work in this regard?" questions were put on the agenda. It is necessary to take measures to form moral and ideological immunity against the evil of corruption in the implementation of preventive works. In order to carry out preventive work, first of all, a vaccine should be developed that serves to form immunity against the effects of negative diseases in the minds of people.

In the development of such a vaccine, enlightened Islam plays a decisive role without any exaggeration. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev, speaking about the fight against the evil of corruption, which is an obstacle to the effective implementation of the reforms implemented in our country today, said: we will not be able to achieve the high goals we set before ourselves, unless all its members are vaccinated with the "honesty vaccine", so to speak. "We need to move from fighting the consequences of corruption to its early prevention." In order to eliminate the evil of corruption, which is an obstacle to the development of society, it is necessary to carry out preventive measures effectively.

For this, first of all, a "vaccine" should be created to inoculate people in the process of prevention. Therefore, the development of the above-mentioned "honesty vaccine" is the most urgent problem facing representatives of enlightened Islam and sociologists. In order to develop such a "vaccine", it is necessary to determine the factors that determine human behavior and to think based on that. It is important to form moral and ideological immunity against the evil of corruption when carrying out preventive work. In other words, corruption has legal and moral

reasons. In order to eliminate the legal cause, it is necessary to form fear of the state in people, and to eliminate the moral cause, it is necessary to form fear of creation.

The main focus should be on the formation of the fear of God, because it is precisely this fear that is lacking today. Why is it that the godless worldview formed on the basis of atheistic education during the time of the Soviets destroyed people's fear of God, and such a situation still has its influence. The importance of this fear is that it also serves to form the fear of the state.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, today, in the fight against corruption, the main attention should be paid to the spiritual and moral education that serves to create fear. In this, it is necessary to achieve spiritual growth on the basis of wider use of the educational opportunities of the enlightened Islamic religion.

In addition, it is necessary to implement measures aimed at studying the anti-corruption law and forming ideological immunity based on instilling the national idea. In the formation of spiritual and ideological immunity, it is necessary to pay special attention to the health of a person's understanding of happiness. Because a person's behavior is shaped by his concept of happiness, if happiness for a person is to be materially rich, then he lives based on the principle that if you have money, it is soup in the forest, and as a result, he falls ill with corruption. Spiritual elevation, which is formed on the basis of enlightened Islam, plays an important role in improving a person's understanding of happiness. Because a spiritually high person considers a happy life not in material wealth, but in the peace and comfort of the body and soul.

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